

RNA ISH ASSAY TO DETECT miRNA OR siRNA

VISUALIZE SMALL RNAs WITH MORPHOLOGICAL CONTEXT AND SPATIAL RESOLUTION

The single-molecule gene expression can be visualized directly in intact tissues with single-cell resolution using RNA *in situ* hybridization (RNA ISH). The assay represents a major advancement with its proprietary probe design to amplify target-specific signals but not background noise from non-specific hybridization. Detecting small RNAs requires a robust, highly specific, and highly sensitive assay with minimal time, ease of effort, and ease of data interpretation. **Creative Bioarray's scientists are experienced using miRNA ISH for compound screening and other research experiments.**

THE miRNA ISH ASSAY IS EXCEPTIONAL FOR THE DETECTION OF:

- Small interfering RNAs (siRNAs)
- microRNAs (miRNAs)
- Antisense oligonucleotides
- Small RNA sequences that are 17-50nt in length

Fig. a

Fig. b

Representative figures show RNA chromogenic *in situ* hybridization (CISH) analyses for ciRS-7 in a poorly differentiated (Fig. a) and a well differentiated (Fig. b) colon adenocarcinoma.

Features of Creative Bioarray's miRNA or siRNA ISH Services:

- **Accuracy**- *In situ* Detection Service – Customized probe design
- **Value**-Quality service guaranteed and with competitive pricing
- **Efficiency**-We can beat the fastest turnaround time of any supplier in the industry

Order Now

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